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ISSUES OF SETTLEMENT OF THE COLONIAL ADMINISTRATION SYSTEM OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE IN TURKESTAN

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Abstract: In this article, the division of Turkestan into three khanates led not only to its political-economic and spiritual-cultural decline, but also to the weakening of the foundations of statehood that governs the country, to the destruction of a single nation and religious faith. It also caused the strengthening of localism in the region.

Enter. In the 50s of the 19th century, Turkestan was a region that suffered from a comprehensive crisis. This crisis was not influenced by other countries, but gradually matured through internal conflicts. The crisis accelerated and created an opportunity for the conquest of the country by the Russian Empire. The interest of the Russian Empire in the wealth of Turkestan began during the reign of Peter I, and preparations for the invasion lasted for a century and a half. In the middle of the 19th century, the interests of two major colonial empires - Great Britain and Russia - collided in Turkestan. Each of them was afraid of Russia's entry into Turkestan. Lieutenant Alexander Byrnes, sent by the East India Company in 1831-1833 to collect espionage information, came from India to Afghanistan and from there to Bukhara as a tourist. Based on the collected evidence and personal observations, he wrote a three-volume book entitled "Travel to Bukhara". In this work, he provided valuable information about Turkestan. The British government opposes the khanates of Bukhara, Khiva and Kokhan against Russia tried to organize a union. In 1841-1842, the British government sent Major Connolly to Khiva and Colonel Stoddart to Bukhara on a special mission. They were in the presence of the Khan of Khiva and the Emir of Bukhara and offered the three khanates to help each other, unite their forces, form an alliance to avoid Russian aggression, and promised to help with troops to fight against the Russian troops. However, due to the lack of official documents, Emir Nasrullah threw them into prison. To save them, Major Wolf was sent to Bukhara under the auspices of Turkey by England, but his attempt in Bukhara in 1843-1845 did not yield results, the prisoners were executed. Wolf himself narrowly escaped. It is also known that Captain Abbott, who came to Khiva in 1843, worked for the interests of

England. The East India Company tried to enter and occupy the markets of Central Asia, to ensure that British goods replaced Russian goods in the markets. In this regard, they also made extensive use of Indian and Iranian merchants. Great Britain's desire to enter and occupy Central Asia worried the Russian Empire. He took advantage of the fact that he was directly bordering the Khanate and started military operations. The conquest of Central Asia by the Russian Empire did not last long from a historical point of view. The process of conquest in 1865-1895 led to the subjugation of Central Asian nations, whose mutual borders were not defined, to the empire. In 1853, in the north-western region of the Khanate, the Governor-General of Orenburg, Perovsky, with a large army, attacked the Kokan Khanate in 1853. captured the strategically important fortress of Akmasjid (now Kyzylorda). According to Russian sources, Muhammad Vali, the commander of the fortress from the first days of the siege of Akmasjid, was killed. 230 people from the defenders of the fortress were killed, 74 people were captured, 35 people were wounded. During the siege, a total of 106 Russians were killed and wounded 22. Due to the Crimean War of 1855-1857, the Russian Empire did not conduct large-scale military operations to conquer Central Asia 23 . In 1860, Governor-General of Siberia Gosford, from the north-eastern side of the Khanate, attacked the military fortifications belonging to the territory of the Kokan Khanate and conquered Tokmok, Pishpak and other fortresses one after another. The military actions of Perovsky and Gosford were actually the beginning of the Russian Empire's undeclared invasion of Central Asia. The issue of conquering Turkestan was discussed by Tsar Alexander II in the council held in 1859 and 1861, and first of all, military actions against the Kokan Khanate were discussed.

decided to start In May 1864, Russian troops under the command of Chernyayev from the east, and Verevkin's troops from the west invaded the territory of the Kokan Khanate. They occupied the important and main cities of the Kokhan Khanate: Avliyoota, Suzaq, Turkestan. The invaders started marching to Shymkent on July 14, 1864. In the meantime, Kokhan Khan Sultan Sayyid Khan and Alimquli Amirakar gathered all their forces and went to battle around Chimket.

prepared. There was a fierce battle for three days. Alimquli Amirakar's troops won the battle, Chernyayev's troops were defeated in the battle and forced to retreat. While Alimquli Amirakar was preparing his troops for battle to liberate the cities occupied by the invaders, it was reported that the Emir of Bukhara, Muzaffar, had invaded the territories of the Khanate of Kokand. Alimquli Amirakar was forced to send his army to defend Kokan against the Bukhara emir, not the invaders. The situation favored Chernyayev, his troops joined the Orenburg detachments in Sayram, organized a new march to Shymkent on September 14, 1864 and captured the city. On October 2, 1864, Chernyayev, who was revengeful for his position and titles, launched an attack on Tashkent. Tashkent is one of the largest and strategically important cities of the Kokhan Khanate, with a population of around 100,000. City

It is divided into Shaikhontakhur, Sebzor, Beshyogoch and Kokcha districts. There were 12 gates, 189 mosques, 10 madrasahs. Tashkent was surrounded by a wall 25 kilometers long, 2-3 meters wide and 5-7 meters high. Thanks to the brave actions of the defenders of Tashkent, Chernyayev suffered a heavy defeat, he lost 72 officers and soldiers in the battle.

Research methodology. During the war, the wealthy nobles of Tashkent supported the defenders. Mullah Salihbek Okhund (1812-1867), the son of Kazakhbek Dodhoh from Tashkent, spent all his wealth for the defense of Tashkent and supported the people financially during the 45-day siege. Chernyayev spent the winter of 1864-1865 with military training. did. His troops were replenished with weapons, new battalions and companies of sappers arrived from Siberia and Orenburg. In the spring of 1865, Chernyayev's new attack began. On April 29, 1865, the Niyozbek fortress surrendered, 25 the dam that diverts water from the Chirchik River to the Kaikovuz Anhor, which supplies Tashkent with water, was demolished, leaving the city's inhabitants without water. Alimquli Amirakar arrived from Kokan to Tashkent with a large army. There were fierce battles for Tashkent. Alimquli Amirakar was seriously

injured and died. Finally, the resistance of the defenders of the city was broken, on June 15, Chernyayev conquered Tashkent. On June 17, Chernyayev negotiates with the influential people of Tashkent and violently insists that the city voluntarily surrender to the Russian troops, that the inhabitants of the city remain in their religion, that affairs are conducted according to Sharia, and that the yard and a bilateral agreement was signed that the gardens will remain in the hands of their owners. Tashkent was made a part of the Russian Empire. As a result, the Turkestan region was formed within the Orenburg General Governorship, and General Chernyayev was appointed as its military governor. On January 28, 1866, a military detachment consisting of 14 companies of soldiers, 600 Cossacks, and 16 cannons was mobilized from Chinoz to Sirdarya 26. But this attack on Jizzakh led by Chernyayev was defeated. After that, due to his arbitrariness, Chernyayev was recalled to St. Petersburg, and General Romanovsky was appointed in his place. The Emir of Bukhara was a spectator while the Russian Empire was occupying the territories of Kokan, but now, when the attack on the territories of the Bukhara Emirate began, Khudoyar Khan, the Khan of Kokan, remained silent. On May 8, 1866, General Romanovsky's march towards Erzhar ended with the defeat of the Bukhara army and the capture of the fortified camp. Amir is forced to flee to Jizzakh. Romanovsky directed the march towards Khojand, as a result of fierce battles on May 19-22, 1866, Khojand was captured. In August 1866, Governor-General Krijanovsky from Orenburg came to Tashkent and, together with Romanovsky, started the movement to subjugate the Bukhara emir. With the help of a large army, in October 1866, Oratepa region, Zomin fortress was captured. It was a big battle for Jizzakh. The city of Jizzakh was surrounded by a two-story wall 4 meters high and 3 meters wide, and had a fortress-like defense. 10,000 defense soldiers in the city, 53 On July 14, 1867, Alexander II issued a decree on the establishment of the General Governorate of Turkestan and the Turkestan Military District. Adjutant-General K. P. von Kaufman was appointed as the governor-general and district commander. He is given the right to declare war, make peace, independently resolve military-administrative, financial-economic, civil affairs. That is why he is known as "Half King". This event was a new stage in the Russian Empire's conquest of Turkestan.

Kaufman started the next march towards Samarkand. On May 1, 1868, on May 1, 1868, he fought with the troops of the Bukhara emir on Cho'ponota hill near the city and easily defeated them. Samarkand, which immediately captured the world, surrendered to the enemy almost without a fight on May 2. Summary. The emir of Bukhara gathered his troops and marched towards Samarkand to repel the enemy. The armies of the two sides clashed in Zirabulok on June 2, 1868, and as a result of a fierce battle, the amir's troops were crushed. Meanwhile, an uprising against the invaders broke out in Samarkand. Governors of Shahrisabz and Kitab Jo'rabek and Bobobek and Abdumalik Tora, the son of the emir, arrived in Samarkand with an army on May 27, and together with the rebels, Colonel Nazarov and Major Shtempel, the military chief, left in Samarkand by Kaufman. who fought fiercely with the parts. The battle lasted 8 days. 275 soldiers were killed and wounded out of 500 enemy forces. Kaufman, who learned about the events in Samarkand, immediately returned to Samarkand and on June 8 ordered the city to be bombarded with cannons, the inhabitants to be shot indiscriminately, and the city to be burned. The population was exterminated, mosques and historical monuments were burned, ancient unique material and spiritual monuments were taken to Petersburg. On June 23, 1868, a peace treaty was signed between Kaufman and Amir Muzaffar. The Emirate of Bukhara was turned into a vassal of the Russian Empire, that is, a state that cannot have independent relations with foreign countries. Zarafshan district was established on June 28, 1868 28 . According to the peace agreement, Khojand, Oratepa, Jizzakh, Samarkand, Kattakorgan were included in the Russian Empire, and the emir undertook to pay compensation of 125,000 gold (500,000 soums). 10,000 gold was immediately collected from the compensation to be paid 29 . The truce, based on such raids and robberies, increased the hatred of the upper classes of the population. The forces of Abdumalik, Jo'rabek and Bobobek were directed not only against the invaders, but also against Amir Muzaffar. They declared Abdumalik as

amir. Amir Muzaffar started a war against his compatriots with the help of Kaufman, not against the invaders, and in August 1870 he suppressed them by force and kept his throne.

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